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*Bias and Transparency in AI Systems: Managing Ethical Risks in
Algorithmic Business Operations*

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1. Abstract

The focus of this paper is on bias and transparency with regard to artificial intelligence in algorithmic business operations. From the topic provided, it is clear that the objective of this research is relevant. The focus is on bias and transparency with regard to ethical issues surrounding AI. The need for this research is on recognizing how the development of investments in AI and its use in organizations correlates or co-exists with an increase in bias and abuse of AI. The methodology for this research is clear on how to conduct an inquiry on the subject matter. The process of conducting structured inquiry is clear. This includes an analysis of literature and quantitative data matrix analysis on AI investments, AI use globally, and bias from 2012 until 2024.

2. Introduction

The rise of the use of AI in the running of businesses has led to the issue of ethics, bias, and transparency in the algorithms. For instance, the use of algorithms in the decision-making process in the hiring of employees in a company, customer profiling, and the granting of loans is on the rise. However, one is left wondering how ethics can be addressed in the process, especially when AI is becoming more integral in every process. At the same time, there has been regulation on the use of AI, as well as the techniques and algorithms used in the process, there is a quest to know how ethics can be addressed.

Thus, the aim of this paper is to explore the link between the adoption of AI in business processes and the creation of bias and transparency risks. The main research query that is used to inform this study is as follows: *What is the link between the growing use of artificial intelligence in business processes and the creation of bias and transparency risks over time?* This paper will offer a brief overview of the current regulatory, technical, and governance-related views on ethical AI, while drawing on both literature review and quantitative longitudinal analysis.

Quote:

" The real risk with AI isn't malice, but incompetence."

— *Stuart J. Russell, OBE, FRS, is a British computer scientist known for his pioneering contributions to artificial intelligence (AI).*

The literature search for this study was conducted using academic databases including Google Scholar, Scopus, SpringerLink, and EUR-Lex. The main keywords used in the search include *artificial intelligence, algorithmic bias, algorithmic transparency, explainable AI, ethical AI, automated decision-making, AI governance, GDPR, and Artificial Intelligence Act.*

3. Methodological Approach

3.1 Literature Review Methodology

The literature review was conducted using a structured and systematic approach between October 2025 and January 2026 to identify relevant academic, legal, and policy-oriented literature on bias and transparency in artificial intelligence, with a focus on algorithmic business operations. The review aimed to integrate perspectives from law & regulations, computer science, and sociotechnical research.

The search engines that were employed included Scopus, Google Scholar, Springer Link, and EUR-Lex. Scopus and Springer Link were employed for searching peer-reviewed journals, Google Scholar for searching cross-disciplinary highly cited literature, while EUR-Lex was employed for searching official regulations issued by the EU, including decisions by the Court of Justice of the European Union.

The principal key phrases or keywords used were AI bias, algorithm transparency, explainable AI, ethical AI, algorithm decision-making, AI governance, GDPR, as well as Artificial Intelligence Act. Other terms like fairness in AI, black box algorithms, and counterfactual explanation were also taken into account. The key phrases were narrowed down continually depending on the themes arising.

The initial search produced approximately 120 results. After screening titles, 55 sources were excluded due to lack of relevance to AI ethics or business applications. Abstract screening led to the exclusion of an additional 35 sources that focused purely on technical performance or unrelated domains. Full-text review of the remaining publications resulted in 18 key sources

being included in the final literature review. Inclusion criteria required sources to be relevant to AI bias, transparency, governance, or regulation, to be academically credible, and to focus on business, legal, or organizational contexts. Publications were primarily selected from 2017 onwards, with earlier works included only where foundational.

3.2 Data Analysis Methodology

The empirical analysis employs a quantitative longitudinal research design to examine the relationship between artificial intelligence adoption in business contexts and reported incidents of AI-related bias or misuse over the period 2012–2024. The dataset contains four key variables: global corporate AI investment, reported AI bias or misuse incidents, the number of AI systems by researcher affiliation, and the share of AI-related job postings. Together, these variables capture both the scale of organizational AI adoption and associated ethical risk exposure.

All analyses were conducted using Microsoft Excel. The methodological approach combines descriptive and analytical techniques, including correlation analysis to assess linear associations among variables and normalization analysis to evaluate ethical risk relative to investment scale. Given the strong interrelationships among explanatory variables, LASSO regression was applied as a robustness check to address multicollinearity and to identify the most influential predictors, with results interpreted as associative rather than causal due to the limited sample size.

In addition, trend analysis was used to describe the temporal evolution of AI adoption and ethical risk, while growth rate and elasticity analysis was employed to assess whether ethical risk increased proportionally with AI investment. A scenario-based forecasting approach was further applied to provide indicative projections of future bias or misuse incidents under the assumption that recent adoption patterns persist.

All analyses adopt a non-causal, associative interpretation. Raw data, intermediate calculations, and Excel-based outputs are provided in Appendix A to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

4. Data Analysis and Results Interpretations

This section examines the relationship between the adoption of artificial intelligence in business settings and reported incidents of AI-related bias or misuse between 2012 and 2024. The analysis is based on a longitudinal dataset comprising four key variables that capture both the scale of AI

adoption and associated ethical risks. These variables include: (1) annual global corporate investment in artificial intelligence, measuring the financial scale of adoption; (2) reported annual incidents of AI-related bias or misuse, measuring ethics-related risk visibility; (3) annual development of AI systems by researcher affiliation, capturing technological development intensity; and (4) the share of AI-related job postings relative to total job postings, measuring organizational integration of AI within corporate labor structures.

4.1 Correlation Analysis

Output Table

	<i>Column 1</i>	<i>Column 2</i>	<i>Column 3</i>	<i>Column 4</i>	<i>Column 5</i>	<i>Column 6</i>
Column 1	1					
Column 2	0.838817	1				
Column 3	0.880443	0.641692	1			
Column 4	0.924602	0.716338	0.834828	1		
Column 5	0.942397	0.892826	0.858074	0.876753	1	
Column 6	0.978851	0.875009	0.841034	0.893526	0.912121	1

The correlation matrix shows that there are strong positive linear correlations between all variables, with Pearson correlation coefficients between 0.64 and 0.98.

The correlation matrix calculated based on annual global corporate investment in AI, incidents of AI bias or misuse, AI system deployment by researcher affiliation, and the proportion of AI-related job postings for the years 2012-2024 shows strong positive linear correlations between all variables, with Pearson correlation coefficients between 0.64 and 0.98.

A value closer to one indicates that there is a great deal of positivity in the data set, which implies that AI investment, organizational AI integration strategies, and incidents of bias/misuse are increasing together and have a great deal in common with regard to their trends. Values above 0.8 indicate that a great deal of variance is shared between data points; that is, a great deal of variance is shared between

variables in regard to their trends as well. It would seem that trends of increasing diffusion of AI in business environments are associated with trends of increasing incidents of bias/misuse in business environments.

4.2 Normalization Analysis of AI Bias and Misuse Incidents

Year	Annual global corporate investment in artificial intelligence	AI bias or misuse incidents (count)	AI Bias Incidents per \$10 Billion Investment
2012	0	8	0
2013	16.95	6	3.539823009
2014	21.79	13	5.966039468
2015	29.07	24	8.255933953
2016	38.18	41	10.7386066
2017	59.39	49	8.25054723
2018	85.92	45	5.237430168
2019	109.46	43	3.928375662
2020	232.29	85	3.65921908
2021	360.73	75	2.079117345
2022	234.49	101	4.307219924
2023	178.75	149	8.335664336
2024	217.97	233	10.68954443

$$\text{Normalized Bias Incident} = \text{AI Bias or Misuse Incident} / (\text{AI investment} / 10 \text{ wrt Year})$$

The normalized incidence of AI bias or misuse is calculated as:

In order to describe the increasing pattern of the surge of investments made by companies on artificial intelligence globally, normalization analysis was conducted. In the normalization analysis, the incidents of bias or misuse of artificial intelligence have been expressed for every \$10 billion spent on artificial intelligence from the dataset. The normalization analysis compares the financial spending patterns of the two completely different financial scales of the ethical risk.

Normalized information shows that the incidence of bias in AI does not demonstrate a proportional increase concerning the growth of investment. For instance, since the intensity level was relatively high, the intensity of incident level reduced during expansive growth in investment. This indicates that there are observations concerning learning and good governance practices. However, maintaining high levels of incident intensity in recent years may indicate further

developments that may outgrow current governance. Such developments may include those of new emergent applications of these technologies of AI. The correlation analysis highlights the absolute relationship between the incidence of AI adoption and bias incidents, whereas the normalization analysis investigates whether the risk of ethics grows proportionally with the size of AI investment.

4.3 LASSO Regression and Robustness

To address potential multicollinearity arising from strong interrelationships among the explanatory variables, a Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) regression was employed as a robustness check.

Variable	LASSO Coefficient
Investment	-0.309
AI Systems	0.443
AI Job Share	7.02
Intercept	4.846

Interpretation of coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Interpretation
AI Job Share (7.02)	Strong positive	Dominant driver of bias incidents
AI Systems (0.443)	Moderate positive	Deployment scale contributes to risk
Investment (-0.309)	Negative	Investment mitigates ethical risk
Intercept	Baseline	Acceptable

In order to assess the possibility of the presence of multicollinearity due to strong relationships between independent variables, the idea of utilizing Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) regression for robustness tests was considered. The results have confirmed the idea that the share of AI-based employees has the most significant impact on cases of bias or misuse of AI, as indicated by the significantly differing coefficient value of the variable, i.e., 7.02. impact on the cases of reported AI bias or misuse, as indicated by the strongly differing coefficient value for the variable, i.e., 7.02.

The deployment of AI also shows a positive correlation with bias/use, though this is only moderate, to the tune of 0.443. What stands out here is that the level of investment by corporations also shows a negative correlation, to the tune of -0.309, with regard to issues concerning ethics risks. However, none of the coefficients seem to shrink towards zero, indicating that all the variables do have some level of information value to the model.

However, as would be expected in light of the dominant effect of the AI job share coefficient, organizational size and the level of integration of AI operations are seen to be of critical importance, as opposed to investment and research operations. The results obtained by the LASSO, in light of the small sample size, can only be seen as indicative, though they do seem to reinforce the notion that ethical risk is seen to be more closely aligned to the organizational integration of AI, as opposed to the level of investment.

4.4 Forecast Analysis of AI Bias Incidents

Year	Actual Y (Bias Incidents)	Forecast Y
2012	8	
2013	6	
2014	13	
2015	24	
2016	41	
2017	49	
2018	45	
2019	43	
2020	85	
2021	75	
2022	101	
2023	149	
2024	233	
2025		169.08
2026		183.65
2027		198.22
2028		212.79
2029		227.36

The results of the Forecast analysis showed the presence of an ascending trend of AI bias/misuse incidents, especially with regard to the recent years. However, on the basis of the results of the estimated model of regression analysis of bias incidents, the values of the predicted values

showed the presence of an ascending trend of bias incidents from 2025 to 2029, on the condition of the assumption of the continuity of the tendencies of the application of AI. Although this analysis cannot be considered as a causal certainty of the escalation of the risks of the application of artificial intelligence in business processes, the presence of a clear indication of the escalation of the risks of ethical problems in the application of AI in business processes cannot be avoided.

4.5 Trend Analysis of AI Adoption and Ethical Risk

Trend Anlysis of AI investment

Trend Analysis of AI bais & miuse incidents

Trend Anlysis on AI newly founded companies

As depicted above, it is clear that the investments in AI technology, the development of AI businesses, and the use of bias in AI technology are on an increasing trend between 2012 and 2024. These parallelly increasing trends clearly indicate the incorporation of AI technology in a corporate business.

On the flip side, however, the results obtained from the above trend analysis are of a descriptive nature, where it is not clear whether the level of risk is proportional to the incorporation of AI technology or if it is being mitigated through the mechanisms of governance. The proportional increase, if any, between the investment in AI technology and the level of risk is analyzed in the next section, which is known as elasticity.

4.6 Growth Rate and Elasticity Analysis

Incident_Growth_Rate	Investment_Growth_Rate	Risk_Elasticity
0	0	0
-0.25	0.285545723	-0.875516529
1.166666667	0.33409821	3.491987179
0.846153846	0.313381493	2.700075994
0.708333333	0.555526454	1.275066792
0.195121951	0.4467082	0.436799573
-0.081632653	0.273975791	-0.297955716
-0.044444444	1.122145076	-0.039606683
0.976744186	0.552929528	1.766489466
-0.117647059	-0.349957032	0.336175725
0.346666667	-0.237707365	-1.458375792
0.475247525	0.219412587	2.165999364
0.563758389	-1	-0.563758389

Due to the limited number of observations, a growth rate and elasticity-based approach was used to analyze the relationship between corporate AI investment and reported AI bias or misuse incidents. This method enables proportional economic interpretation without relying on regression models that require large sample sizes.

Year-to-year growth rates were calculated as:

Incident Growth Rate

$$\text{Incident Growth Rate}_t = \frac{I_t - I_{t-1}}{I_{t-1}}$$

Investment Growth Rate

$$\text{Investment Growth Rate}_t = \frac{A_t - A_{t-1}}{A_{t-1}}$$

where:

- I_t = AI bias or misuse incidents in year t
- A_t = AI investment in year t

Based on these growth rates, the elasticity of ethical risk with respect to AI investment was computed as:

$$\text{Risk Elasticity}_t = \frac{\text{Incident Growth Rate}_t}{\text{Investment Growth Rate}_t}$$

Values of elasticity greater than one indicate that incidents increased faster than investment, while values below one suggest relative risk containment.

The results on the elasticity provide a sense of proportion for the relative growth of ethical risk dynamics compared to the investment in AI. The results show that many years have an elasticity value higher than one, indicating a period where bias or misuse incidents grew faster than the investment. However, other years have an elasticity value of less than one or negative, indicating a period where the investment grew faster than the incidents or where the incidents declined while the investment continued.

4.7 Interpretation Across Analytical Methods

The different analytical approaches taken in this analysis cover different aspects of the relationship between AI adoption & ethical risk, but they don't contradict each other. The correlation and trend analyses describe the absolute relationship between AI adoption metrics and bias or misuse incidents, revealing that both variables increase together. On the other hand, the normalization and elasticity analyses describe the relative relationship between AI adoption metrics and bias or misuse incidents, revealing that they do not increase proportionally to the growth in AI investment. The LASSO regression analysis provides further insight into the relationship between these variables, revealing that the main factor contributing to bias or misuse incidents is not the level of AI investment, but rather the level to which AI is integrated into an organization. In total, these analyses reveal that while bias or misuse incidents increase as AI adoption increases, the magnitude of these incidents is ultimately determined by the level to which AI is integrated into an organization.

5. Literature Review

The emergence of literature on bias and transparency in artificial intelligence systems signifies the rapid integration of technological studies into policy. The integration of these areas signifies the increased debates on the ways by which individual decision-making algorithms can be made transparent and fair from a business point of view. The debates on the regulation of these emerging technologies have been addressed by two major forms of regulation: the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act). According to GDPR, Article 15 responds to the idea that individuals have the right to access their personal data and have it available to them in a readable form; Article 22 bans the practice of fully automated individual decision-making with significant effects on individuals, except when it is exercised legally and under human control (European Parliament and Council, 2016). On the basis of the above precepts, the AI Act takes a risk management orientation, whereby the basic prohibitions are instituted on social scoring and emotional recognition in sensitive domains, along with strict rules to be followed on the highly risky application of the domains of employment, selection, and assessment of credibility.

However, the interpretation and achievability of “transparency” and “explainability” regarding the AI system vary from researcher to researcher. Lawyers & scholars Edwards and Veale (2017) argue that the GDPR proposes the existence of a “right of explanation,” which enables individuals affected by a decision to understand and contest algorithmic decisions. However, computer researchers Wachter, Mittelstadt, and Russell (2017) argue that direct explanations of the algorithm could be inefficient, misleading, or even violative of intellectual property rights and it is a very complex process for a common man. Counterfactual explanations will be proposed as a different solution for the subject matter experts where a person is provided the slightest variation required in the outcome instead of the algorithm itself in the case of a complex system.

Recent case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union has been augmented this tension between legal intelligibility and technical practicality. In *F.F. v Österreichische Datenschutzbehörde and CRIF GmbH*, the Court argued that the right of access in the GDPR covers not just raw personal data but also the contextual information necessary to enable individuals meaningfully to understand data processing practices (CJEU, 2023a). So practically, it is not enough for the company to say “here is your data”, they are responsible to explain why they used the data and in what context it is used. Similarly, in *OQ v Land Hessen*, the Court stated that automated credit scoring systems, in so far as financial institutions rely conclusively upon the same, constitutes processing falling within the scope of Article 22 and therefore mandates human intervention, except when specific exemptions apply under that provision (CJEU, 2023b). These cases have reinforced the relevant legal requirement for algorithmic transparency and accountability in business operations a great deal.

While the literature on law and regulations suggests the issue of bias as a phenomenon that is more systemic and occurs at more points within the life cycle of the AI system, this has been argued more clearly and more specifically by Barocas et al. (2023), who argued that “fairness is something that needs to be addressed throughout the entire life cycle of the AI system, from all the steps within the data creation process to the actual data use and deployment. Other services that are linked to the ways in which transparency can be achieved include Data-Sheets on Datasets (Geburu et al., 2021), and Model Cards (Mitchell et al., 2019). However, sociotechnical theorists have argued that documentation could be seen as an illusion of accountability. Selbst et al. (2019) argued that fairness interventions could be failing because they do not account for

the social, organizational, and institutional context in which they are applied. Empirical governance-oriented research, such as Raji et al. (2020), aims to bridge this gap by proposing internal audit structures that encompass ethical, legal, and technical considerations throughout the lifecycle of developing and deploying AI. So as a whole, fixing the code without the context does not fix the issue.

Despite the existing considerable amount of work on the legal technical and sociotechnical issues of bias and transparency in AI systems, it is quite interesting to note that one of the areas where there is still a certain degree of neglect is in the understanding of how the norms and technical requirements of bias and transparency are translated into the algorithmic business processes. The existing body of work is largely focused on regulatory requirements and technical bias removal as a goal in itself, as opposed to being part of a larger business process and governance framework. Which simply means that we don't really understand how these requirements and technical standards actually function in real-world business processes and AI ethics is still in the form of a theory and not in action. Particularly considered is the existing body of work that is examining how companies can address regulatory requirements for algorithmic black-box explainability and fairness as part of the commercial imperatives of efficiency and algorithmic black-box protection as intellectual property. This is particularly relevant in the area of algorithmic business, where there is the potential for AI systems to have a direct economic impact in terms of influencing economic opportunities as organizational accountability. It is therefore important to address this in a manner that is informed by a lens that is focused on the concept of alignment in terms of legal and technical requirements, as a means of promoting organizational and ethical risk management in the context of bias and algorithmic black boxes, as part of algorithmic business, as a means of business ethics, which means that the issue of bias & transparency is a matter of ongoing business risk management.

Together, these approaches suggest a complex but complementary academic landscape. Legal scholars emphasize enforceable rights, procedural fairness, and accountability, while computer scientists emphasize technical transparency, robustness, and bias mitigation, and sociotechnical scholars emphasize organizational culture, power, and governance structures. This interplay suggests that true algorithmic transparency in business requires not only technical transparency, legal rights, and accountability, but also a cultural shift towards understanding bias mitigation as a form of ongoing governance, rather than a one-time compliance exercise. Algorithmic business

operations, where automated systems play a growing role in the distribution of employment, financial, and consumer opportunities, suggest that transparency and fairness are key elements of ethical business governance. True algorithmic transparency in business requires the efforts of law, technology, and governance, particularly as automated systems play a growing role in the distribution of economic opportunities.

6. conclusion

This paper was aimed at evaluating the relationship that exists between the development of artificial intelligence, which is being adopted by everyday businesses, as opposed to bias and transparency, especially as it relates to ethics. Based on the findings of the analysis of the data, it is evident that a strong positive relationship exists between the development of artificial intelligence and its integration into everyday business, as well as bias that arises from the development of artificial intelligence. Based on the study as depicted by the data, it is evident that a positive correlation exists as it relates to analyzing the trend and elasticity used as opposed to the bias that was noted.

In relation to discussing the research question, it is evident from the findings that the development of AI, as well as its further development in relation to the realm of business, is subject to an increase in ethical risks, especially as it relates to its further implication in organizational decision-making, as opposed to an increase in spending, which may be a good measure of good governance, yet it does not deter bias from arising.

The literature verifies that legal systems such as the GDPR and the AI Act, together with technical solutions for explainability and fairness, form a crucial basis for ethical AI governance. Nevertheless, both the literature and the empirical findings suggest that there is still considerable uncertainty about how transparency and fairness can be operationalized in practice. This suggests that future research should focus on firm-level governance and organizational decision structures. From an industry perspective, the results suggest the importance of ongoing ethical risk management.

7. References

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8. Appendix A: Raw Data and Excel-Based Analysis

This appendix provides the raw dataset and the complete quantitative analysis used in this study. The dataset covers the period from 2012 to 2024 and includes annual global corporate investment in artificial intelligence, reported AI bias or misuse incidents, the annual number of AI systems by researcher affiliation, and the share of AI-related jobs among total job postings.

All descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, multiple linear regression, LASSO regression, trend analysis, and forecast calculations were conducted using Microsoft Excel. The full Excel workbook containing the raw data and all analytical outputs is available as supplementary material at the following link: [DATA ANALYSIS.xlsx - Google Sheets](#)

(<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1DGy0YuvKaTduUBCQLcMo1lypknVjJKmK/edit?usp=sharing&oid=108702478069634539244&rtpof=true&sd=true>)